

Society survival theory and the contemporary age: proposal of a system approach

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Abstract

We present in this article a first system approach to the society survival theory. This theory predicts the emergency of some new socio-economic structures and their ideological supra-structures. The causes of these emergencies are pressures and punctual crises. Thus, the evolution of societies is not described by a linear and progressive vision, as a consequence of progress. Oppositely, the society survival theory defends the existence of some mechanisms of survival that are present in all type of societies and in any historic stage. The future mathematical model, based on this system approach, should simulate these mechanisms that would contribute, for instance, to understand the fall of the Ancient Regime and the emergence of the First French Republic. The French Revolution was the most important event of the beginning of Contemporary Age, and it was a great important event for the development of the contemporary world. This event is explained through the society survival theory.

Resumen

En este artículo se presenta una primera aproximación sistémica de la teoría de la supervivencia de las sociedades. Esta teoría predice el surgimiento de nuevas estructuras socio-económicas y de la supra-estructura ideológica que las acompaña, a partir de presiones y crisis puntuales. Por tanto, se aparta de una visión lineal y progresiva de la evolución de las sociedades, que considera que es el progreso y la razón la que conduce la historia desde la barbarie hasta la civilización. La teoría de la supervivencia de las sociedades defiende la existencia de unos mecanismos de supervivencia que se presentan en todo tipo de sociedades y en cualquier etapa histórica. El futuro modelo matemático basado en esta aproximación sistémica debería poder simular los mecanismos de supervivencia que contribuyeron a la caída del Antiguo Régimen y propiciaron la I República Francesa. El acontecimiento más importante del comienzo de la Edad Contemporánea, la Revolución Francesa, de gran importancia para el devenir del mundo, y ésta es explicada a través de la teoría de la supervivencia de las sociedades.

Key words: Society Survival Theory, Ideology, Crisis, Ancient Regime, First French Republic.

1. Introduction

During Contemporary Age the ideals of citizenship, nationalism, racism (imperialism), democracy and international cooperation arose and consolidate. A fundamental event that gave

origin to Contemporary Age is the French Revolution.

The society survival theory (Amigó, 2001) claims that ideologies constitute supra-structures that arise and consolidate themselves as a result of social crises.

The society survival theory proposes the same and unique mechanism of change that plays in all societies and historic ages. When a society suffers a crisis, it resolves it choosing one of the potential possible options. As a consequence, a new ideology arises. Once a determined option has been "selected", it is consolidated simultaneously with the new ideology. This new ideology is conserved until a new crisis demands a change. Some possible options to solve a crisis are: 1) New social structure; 2) Persistence of the social structure; 3) Recover of a prior social structure; 4) Social changes of transition to a new social structure.

Thus, the society survival theory does not support a linear and progressive vision of history. Societies do not evolve of a natural manner toward a greater level of civilization and perfection. Besides, crises have a great importance in history, as Gianbattista Vico asserted in the seventeenth century. Contemporary authors, such as Toynbee (1987), consider crisis as stunning of historic cycles. The society survival theory considers that crises, but not tendency to civilization, are the causes that induce to social and ideological changes.

In this article a system approach to the society survival theory and its postulates is provided. To do this, we support our approach with an example: the change from the Ancient Regime to the French Republic in France, in the 18th century.

There exists a *society system* that tends to equilibrium. This system is constituted by four subsystems (see Figure 1):

1. Subsistence subsystem (population and resources and their interrelationships).
2. Political subsystem (government way, social order).
3. Economy subsystem (production system, economic relationships, trade).
4. Ideology subsystem (values and beliefs shared by the members of a society).

Output variables that must be considered: conflicts, natural catastrophes, ideological influences. These variables trouble the system and move it away from equilibrium, i.e., they threat the system stability. If disequilibrium overcomes a given threshold, then the system changes itself. The concrete cause that produces the overcoming of the threshold (crisis) can be identified many times. The new society system tends the equilibrium.

In addition, the inner dynamics can drive the system to disequilibrium as well. Instances of such disequilibrium are a possible difference between population-needs and produced resources, or the emergence of a new social class due to changes in the production relationships.

2. The beginning of the Contemporary Age

Contemporary Age, from French Revolution until our days, is presented as a historic step of social achievements and ideological developments without comparison. The economic development, from Industrial Revolution, has enabled a progressive improvement of the conditions of life. Besides, the progressive development of science and technology has to be also considered. Furthermore, the ideals of equality and democracy have been raised and consolidated, as well as nationalism and international solidarity.

The society survival theory can explain this progressive ascent of social welfare, as well as the conquest of liberty and equality of Contemporary Age. In addition, this theory can explain also the large social changes in history and in complex societies. These changes are the consequence of the historic events that have happened for long periods of time.

We present a first system approach to the society survival theory. This approach must derive, in a future, in an abstract model suitable to each particular case of social change, such as the theory forecasts. As a first application case of the society survival theory, we study the conditions that unchained the French Revolution. This revolution transformed the political system of the Ancient Regime into a Republic and into a subsequent Empire. This fact supposed also the consequent change in ideology.

3. Application case: The French Revolution and the mechanisms of survival

From a general point of view, the ideological subsystem is composed by the social values shared by a community. We present here an application case when the ideological subsystem changed by a crisis: **the** French Revolution of 1789. It detonated a new social order and a new ideology from **the** Ancient Regime to Republic.

The society system of the Ancient Regime is composed for four systems:

1. **Subsistence system.** Increase of population and recourse exploitation in the 18th century. Lack of resources.
2. **Political subsystem.** Government Form: Illustrated Despotism. Social Order: a hierarchical society that impedes the social ascent to power of the lower classes and of the incipient bourgeoisie.
3. **Economic subsystem.** Economic Mercantilism: the wealth of the world is fixed and one must get the greatest possible part. Industry is organized in the artisanal studio and the work in household. The technology and productivity are fixed and developed very slowly.
4. **Ideological subsystem.** Religious Foundation: the power of king emanates from God, as in the absolutism of the century XVII. A value associated with the Illustrated Despotism is the "paternalism of State" ("all for the town but without the town").

There are some emphasized output variables:

1. International Relationships:
 - Boom of the Illustrated Despotism in many countries of the continent, such as Spain, Russia, Austria, Portugal and Prussia.
 - The wars between European nations looking the hegemony politics.
 - The wars of Luis XIV in the Low Countries and the Sacrum Empire.
2. Periods of sparse harvests.

The new society system that will arise from the French Revolution is characterized by:

1. Subsistence subsystem: Greater fit between population and resources.
2. Political subsystem. Government Form: Constitutional Republic. Social Order: Permeability among social classes. Access to power of the bourgeoisie.
3. Economical system. Free trade: Economic liberty. Machinism: Industrial development and production.
4. Ideological subsystem. Government Foundation: Equality of citizens under law. The nation as integrated ideology. Influences of Parliamentary regime in the

United Kingdom and the United States (output variables).

How is possible a change so radical between the socio-economic system of the Ancient Regime and the Republic in a so short period of time? The society survival theory predicts that:

1. There exist some factors of stability and equilibrium in the Ancient Regime that enable its conservation.
2. In a precise moment, the unbalancing factors put pressure on the maintenance of the Ancient Regime, provoking a crisis.
3. Punctual events unchain the change and surge a new order.
4. The new order is consolidated due to the rising of a new ideology, which could have been developing from very long before.

The factors of stability of the Ancient Regime already have been cited before. The unbalancing factors of the Ancient Regime represent strong tendencies. Many of these tendencies started in historic previous stages. We could focus these tendencies in distinct areas:

1. Thought: Renaissance, Humanism and Illustration. Nationalism.
2. Economy: development of the mechanism and beginning of the Industrial Revolution in the United Kingdom.
3. Social Order: boom of the bourgeoisie that pressures to reach power.

Among the punctual events that precipitated the crisis, there are mainly two:

1. Economic grave crisis in France from 1760 due to the bad harvest, upturn of prices and financial crisis due to the expenses that caused the warlike conflicts.
2. Declaration of the independence of the United States in 1775. In 1783, the British Crown signed the peace and in 1789 George Washington is named the first president of the United States.

The new social order that arose from the crisis was the Republic, proclaimed in 1792. The ideology that surged from this change of socio-economic structure, and consolidated the changes, has been exposed formerly. Its bases legitimize the nations to express in a constitution its legal mark.

Some European countries felt threatened by the events in France and declared the war. Thus, in 1792, the war with Austria and Prusia started.

This situation of war, and the economic crisis in France, provoked the power of Napoleon. He would restore an empire to consolidate the revolutionary ideal both in the country and in abroad.

4. Conclusions

We have presented a first system approach of the society survival theory. The basic ideas have been extracted from the work of Amigó (2001). This approach considers that all societies constitute a basic *society system* composed by four subsystems, in order to explain the human social evolution and crises that change them.

The systems considered are: subsistence, economical, political and ideological systems. The basic relationships model is presented in Figure 1.

The concepts of society survival theory have been translated to systems theory language. Thus, society's tendency to stability is the tendency of the system to equilibrium. Crises are the stunning of changes in equilibrium states (steady states). The emergency of a new society system (new structure) is the qualitative transformation after overcoming the threshold of disequilibrium. Societies transform themselves as a response to pressures that are collectively perceived as threatening their survival (expectation of a catastrophe).

In this context, a first application case is presented. We have focused our work in the ideological subsystem presented in the previous social system to the French Revolution.

French Revolution marks the beginning of Contemporary Age. The socioeconomic and ideological consequences of this great happening are fundamental to understand most our recent history and our current world.

The society survival theory was proposed to explain the mechanisms of survival that have contributed to the change of social structure and of ideology from Ancient Regime to the I Republic in France.

All socio-economic structure and ideological supra-structure have to be conserved while pressures that threaten the stability do not exist. When the social, economic and ideological pressures (which constitute the ideological system) are considerable, it is sufficient that some few punctual facts occur to unchain a crisis. From crisis a new socio-economic structure and a new ideology will arise. Its

function will be to preserve and to keep the new order.

Thus, without rejecting the influence of other historical facts, the society survival theory predicts great changes in civilization. They are due, fundamentally, to crises and threatening to the survival of a determined social order. Therefore, the complexity of the ideological subsystem is the motor of the society evolution. The idea of a progressive tendency toward major levels of civilization, based on rationale, have to be left aside.

This system approach must explain the dynamics of survival mechanisms. In future investigations we will include other factors that have not been considered here, such as the impact of economic cycles in social crises. The theory of economic cycles started with the work of Mitchell (1927), Kondratieff (1935), and Schumpeter (1939). It has been developed afterwards by authors as Lucas (1975), Kydland and Prescott (1982). There exists an alternative theory to the deterministic theory of cycles given by the models of stochastic fluctuations (Maldenbrot, 1963; Keeps and Stanley, 1995), which we will have to consider as well.

The cyclic fluctuations are elements to be included in survival dynamics. In this sense, the long cycles of Arrighi (1994, 1999) have very high influence on the perspective of the world-system of Wallerstein (1979).

In a future time, we intend to develop the model here sketched including a mathematical formulation and elements of complexity. This is also a way to integrate natural and social sciences, in order to have a better understanding of reality.

6. References

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